

A QUALITATIVE STUDY ON THE SLANG WORDS AND SOCIO-CULTURAL EXPRESSIONS OF THE PAMPANGOS

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ABSTRACT

This study is designed to find out the commonly used slang words and socio-cultural expressions of the Pampangos. The Pampangos or Kapampangan people are settling at the heart of Central Luzon in the Philippines. They are considered to be one of the largest ethnolinguistic groups in the country and are also known for their diverse cultures and practices. The research is intended to know how the language users use the slang words and the sociocultural usage of such words in their communicative settings. Thus, the researcher managed to form a conclusion supported by the theories and principles of language. This paper also provided information regarding the formation, evolution and adaptation of the Pampango socio-cultural expressions. The researcher applied the principle and strategy of thematic analysis as a method of qualitative research where in actual interview with the participants was applied and the process of transcribing the interview was also utilized. The study has identified the slang words and socio-cultural expressions of the Pampangos such as pu or opu, patawas me, bari-bari apu, tawu, taksyapo, dyandirit, misdan a yatut, pasirkulatuk, borbolen, o-jo, alang-atdo, arya, keni, diyablus, salibatbat and atin yang ditak. The said terminologies and expressions were also analyzed using the principles of language. The researcher presented in the result of the study the determined socio-cultural expressions using Austin's theories of illocutionary acts, Searle's principles of speech acts and Halliday's principles of the functions of language.

Keywords: *Pampangos, Slang, Socio-cultural, Expressions, Principles, Language*

INTRODUCTION

Language is said to be the most effective and powerful tool of communication. Hymes (1964) pointed out that one may view language as a powerful and essential means of human communication. It is through language that every person is bound by common objectives and norms. Language plays an important role in understanding people, their social and cultural environment. Halliday (1975) also added that Language is used to ensure social maintenance. In a wider sense, this function refers to all uses of language which help to define and maintain groups: teenage slang, family jokes, professional jargon, ritualistic exchanges, social and regional dialects.

It is through language that the culture of a certain speech community is inculcated. Hence, Language and Culture are always related. Culture pertains to the general views of a people in their society. These general views are based on their beliefs, traditions and socioeconomic living which unite them through common goals and perceptions. Every individual belongs to a culture that helps and molds him about his role in the society. Moreover, this culture serves as his foundation in attaining quality of life. The essence of culture is being passed through generations with the use of a dynamic code called “language”. While the child learns his native tongue, he also acquires his culture. The words which were included in the lexical context of a language are strong indicators of the kind of practices people apply in their social settings which replicate their cultural identities.

The lexical context of a Language involves the things that the respective speaking communities value in their own means. For instance, the Filipinos have various terminologies on the different types of rice like palay, bigas, kanin, lugaw and sinangag. There are also more terminologies on its kind like malagkit, denorado, wagwag and sinandomeng while in the American setting the only term for bigas is rice. That’s why they also have the terminologies like rice grain and fried rice and more. The Filipinos don’t have native word for “snow” but we only adapt the Spanish word “nieve” to refer to it. Therefore, Language is the one that crafts the essence of a certain culture. It is also the one that connects one culture to another.

Every society has a native language. A society is composed of a speech community which involves people with different social orientation based on their socioeconomic status, ethnicities and roles that they play. One of the bases of language variations is the differences of the group of people which are embodied in the structure of a society. This variation is called “sociolect”. Such examples are differences between the vocabulary of children to the adults, gay lingos or secret gay codes called “argot” which are commonly used in the mainstream and the language differences between males and females. In relation to this, every person in the society has his own way of language use and this is called “idiolect”. This is influenced by the setting where he grew up with and the place where he belongs. Another language variation is the “register” which is defined according to its use in social situation. As what Halliday points out that this pertains to the level of formalities of language and a complex scheme of communicative behavior. Such examples are the formal speech, non-formal speech, slang and vulgar speech.

This study is focused on the slang words and socio-cultural expressions that are widely and commonly used by Pampangos. The Kapampangan people or Pampangos live in the provinces of Pampanga, Tarlac and some parts of Zambales. The paper attempted to give justifications on how socio-cultural words are commonly used, adapted or formed. Moreover, it also aimed to find out the cultural use of those words among language users.

Cultural word is a word that only exists in a particular language. It is supported by Baker (1992) who said that “cultural word may express a concept which is totally unknown in other culture”. In addition, cultural word means a word that involves culture in which culture itself, according to Hornby (1995) is “art, literature, music, or other intellectual expression of a particular society or time”. To conclude, cultural word is a specific word for special kinds of “things”, “events” or “customs”, which only exist in one language that cannot be translated literally, because it will distort its meaning.

Agoncillo (1990) stated that the ancient Filipinos, which include the Kapampangans had a culture that was basically Malayan in culture and form. They had written languages that traced their origin to the Austronesian parent-stock and used them as media of daily communication and as a vehicle of their expression of their literary moods. Among the Philippine languages, Tagalog and Pampangan show a close affinity to the Malay language, whether Bahasa Indonesia or that of Malaya.

Salitang kalye (from Spanish, calle or "street"), salitang kanto (street corner) and salitang balbal are the Tagalog terms for "slang". Kalye means "street", thus salitang kalye implies that "slang" is pedestrian language. Kanto means "street corner" where most bums while their time away. Dumas & Lighter (1978) defined slang as the use of highly informal words and expressions that are not considered standard in the speaker's dialect or language. Even within a single language community, slang tends to vary widely across social, ethnic, economic, and geographic strata. Slang sometimes grows more and more common until it becomes the dominant way of saying something, at which time it is regarded as mainstream, acceptable language (e.g. the Spanish word caballo), while at other times it may fall into disuse. Numerous slang terms pass into informal mainstream speech, and sometimes into formal speech, though this may involve a change in meaning or usage.

Filipinos were the ones who coined informal terms such as yosi (cigarette), syota (girlfriend), and sosi (social). The gay community is also proud of its own contributions to the Pinoy slang dictionary: Words such as bagets (young), chika (chat), tsimay (housemaid), and jowa (partner) among others. Pinoy slang is also formed by giving new meaning to already existing Filipino words. Examples of these include ahas (snake, for traitor) and ube (color violet, to mean 100 pesos). In general, Filipinos are fond of inventing words and borrowing foreign terms and use them to add spice to their spoken language. The value of slang in the society will show the dynamicity of language specifically at modern times. It involves and shows culture of language speakers in many walks of life. As what Taylor (1985) said “the range of human desires, feelings, emotions and hence, meanings is bound up with the level and type of culture, which in turn is inseparable from the distinctions and categories marked by the language which people

speak". The researcher believes that slang processing is a linguistic phenomenon that needs to be considered and must be a subject for academic study.

There are ways regarding the formation of street words in the Philippine setting. Some street words are adapted from the native dialects like *gurang* (Bicol), *bayot* (Cebuano) and *dako* (bisaya). Others are formed by borrowing from foreign languages like the words *pikon* (pick on, English), *tong* (Chinese) and *Chika* (Spanish). Filipinos also are fond of giving new meaning on the tagalog words like *hiyas* or *gem* (which may mean virginity) and *damo* or *grass* (which may mean marijuana). There are also shortened words like *munti* (*muntinlupa*) and *Kano* (*Amerikano*).

Partridge (1979) indicated in his study that slang also has its purpose. He said the people use street words as an exercise of wit and ingenuity. People are fond of making things funny out of words. In addition, street words are ways of enhancing positivity and reducing negativity. In some aspects it falls as motivation to overcome life's problems. Slang can also be a reference of a person in building contacts with his colleagues and develop the sense of belongingness. He even reiterated on the essence of showing that one belongs to a certain school, trade, or profession, artistic or intellectual set or social class.

Kemmer (2001) explained that it is part of the cultural history of language speakers that they have always adopted loanwords from the languages of whatever cultures they have come in contact with. For example, the word "Para" which is a term always used by Filipinos to stop a jeepney, comes from the Spanish word "Parar" which means to stop. Historically based, Philippines had been colonized by Spain, and the 400 years of Spanish supremacy in the country has its eternal influence to the Filipino language. For example, the Spanish word for table, which is "la mesa" has the same usage in Tagalog. Time keeping in Tagalog is also Spanish, like, "a la una y media," which is 01:30.

Coulmas (1989) pointed out that Language Adaptation examines the process by which a speech community is forced to adopt an active role in making its language suitable for changing functional requirements. He further exemplified that Language Adaptation is a particular aspect of language change, and thus establishes a link between the social and historical study of language. He added that the concept of language adaptation assumes that the speech community is capable of changing its language to meet new communicative needs.

According to Coulmas (1989), the concept of language adaptation assumes that the speech community is capable of changing its language to meet new communicative needs, as German, English, Japanese, and others have. He explained that Language adaptation is usually a gradual and continuous process that goes almost unnoticed by the speech community that can occur by conscious intervention in a linguistic crisis and this can become a political goal involving cultural and linguistic values. Behaviorists view the process of language acquisition as a building process that results from interaction with the environment. (Austin, 1975)

Skinner (1957) also believed that language is acquired through principles of conditioning, including association, imitation, and reinforcement. On the other hand, Hoffer (2002) defined borrowing as the process of importing linguistic items from one linguistic system into another, a process that occurs any time two cultures are in contact over a period of time. Speakers may adopt the item or idea and the source language word for each. Thus, it is believed then that when mindset of the language is acquired, adapted, imitated in a society, the language is being accepted and being integrated in the people, then it becomes already cultural.

Research Questions

The main purpose of this study is to identify and analyze the slang words and socio-cultural expressions of the Pampangos applying the processes and principles of Thematic Analysis. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the commonly used slang words and socio-cultural expressions of the Pampangos?
2. What are the meanings and the formation processes of the Pampango slang words and socio-cultural expressions?

METHODOLOGY

This study applied qualitative research design. Kirk and Miller (1986) mentioned that qualitative research is a distinct tradition in social science that is based on observations of people in their own region and communication with these individuals in their own language and dialect. The researcher used the interview method with the help of linguistic research. The data were gathered through interview and were treated and discussed qualitatively.

The participants of this study constitute 15 informants who are native residents of Tarlac city, Tarlac in Central Luzon. The participants were asked to articulate words and sentences using their native dialect. Those words and sentences were based on the questions being asked about the slang words and socio-cultural expressions of the Pampango language users. The data were listed and analyzed using the method of thematic analysis.

The prepared questions for face-to-face communication served as the primary instrument in gathering the required data. The researcher conducted the interview with the participants' permission in order to get correct and accurate data. The approach guaranteed confidentiality during the interviews. The researcher also explained what is the study all about and how the interview will be kept confidential. In order to answer the above problems, the questions were carefully asked. Data gathered through the interview

were also analyzed and interpreted with the help of language concepts and theories. The use of underlying principles of language added consistency to the research findings.

To make sure that the data gathered are accurate and complete, the researcher reviewed the results of the interview. Transcribing was done simultaneously while the interview is on-going; however, further validation was also done during the review. After which, a thorough analysis of the data was done for categorization of words and expressions. Lastly, as an output of this study, detailed data about the slang words and socio-cultural expressions of the Pampango language users was determined and tabulated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the results and discussion on the study about the slang words and socio-cultural expressions of the Pampango language users. The commonly used terminologies were identified through the interview with the respondents.

Determined Commonly Used Slang Words and Socio-Cultural Expressions of the Pampangos

Opu/pu

Based on the respondents' answers, it is an expression that is similar with the Tagalog words "*opo*" and "*po*". These two words are considered in the Kapampangan communities as the most civilized forms of address specifically when the young ones are talking to the elders.

This terminology is commonly used to show respect and obedience towards the elders as they are really given so much value or importance in the community. These two famous words would literally mean yes when somebody acknowledges or answers the question with gratitude.

Meyatu

The Kapampangan community is rich in old beliefs and traditions. Many of the people still believe on the primitive or traditional way of healing sickness. The word "*meyatu*" (nabati in Tagalog) means "being harmed by a certain supernatural force". There are believers who used to go with the *albularyos* (faith healers) to seek healing for their illnesses. The healers are the ones who declare what particular supernatural force is responsible for one's suffering or sickness. Based on the said conversation, someone is said to be harmed by a supernatural being called "*tikbalang*" and it is responsible for the sickness. In this case, the one who is sick is then advised to do the "*atang*" or offering for him to get healed. This is a common practice not only in the Pampango community but also in other places in the Philippines.

Patawas me

This term would also mean “*ipatawas mo*” in Tagalog. This is done when someone suffered from a serious sickness and is brought to the albularyo (faith healer) to detect the cause of such sickness. “*Patawas*” is a common word in the community because many of the Pampangos still believe in it. They also believe that someone has this extraordinary power to detect pain or sickness. Faith healers are still present in many communities in Pampanga and Tarlac.

Bari-bari apu

This word is a cultural expression of those people who bare respect when it comes to the unseen beings that can harm humans. This is being uttered whenever somebody walks along along the road at night or any private locations which have no lights. The Kapampangans believe that the unseen beings are just out there and they have to be respected. If not, this will cause problems or chaos such as curse, sickness or even deaths.

Tawu

This word is common among Pampangos during festivities and other social and cultural celebrations. There are religious festivities designed for the saints and patrons of different social groups. In the province of Tarlac for example, the well-known patrons such as Maria Corazon, Lourdes, Santa Catalina and Imaculada Concepcion are among patrons which are annually celebrated through fiestas (festivities).

During these occasions, the Kapampangan culture is being showcased by having different foods and delicacies to serve. These are called “*tawu*” or “*handa*” in Tagalog. People recognize Pampanga as the Food capital of the Philippines. This is the reason why food preparation is culturally attributed especially during significant occasions. Even Undas (All Souls Day) and Mahal na Araw (Lenthen Season) are significant days where in the folks prepare for “*tawu*” or food.

Taksyapo/taknaydo

It is other known as “*hayup*” (*bitch*) that is mostly used in a very funny tone. This has various usages according to the intention of the speakers. This terminology could either be taken seriously or a form of joke.

Dyandirit

This expression is commonly used by the young ones especially those who are always out of the house. A Pampango slang word which expresses that something will not be done or accomplished by a person. This means affirmation that somebody will not be able to do or finish a thing.

Misdan a yatut

This is an expression which means “naïve” or “*tatanga-tanga*”. It has another Pampango counterpart called “*mulala*” which also means “tanga”. When somebody commits mistake, the person will say “*misdan a yatut*” or naïve. This word might really mean negative if the context is negatively serious. But most of the time, this expression is taken as a joke.

Pasirkulatuk

The term is specifically referred to a child whose nickname needs to be changed because the elders believe that it is not a good name. Many people believe in superstition and it is evident in the Pampango setting. If a child keeps on suffering from severe illness, the elder would advise the parents to change his name. The elders also agree that replacing or changing the child’s nickname would mean that they also intend to stop the curse.

Borbolen

This word is a negative expression when somebody did something wrong. The word “*Borbolen*” means “crazy” or “out of his mind”. Other people use the words like “*baliw*” and “*bugok*” to mean crazy.

O-jo

It was derived from the tagalog slang expression which is “*Oh Jowa*” which means “*Oh honey*” or “*Oh my love*”. This expression is used as a form of endearment between two lovers. This is simply an expression of love or liking.

Alang-atdo

This term is the other version for “*alang atdong mapait*” or “*walang mapait na apdo*” (*walang isip*) in the Pampango setting. This is used to show that someone is not doing well with something because of his negative attitude. This expression is mostly used by the elders to make their children realize their mistakes.

Arya

This is the Pampango word for “*pamahiin*” or superstitious belief. Pampango community is rich in superstitious belief that even the present generation of the Kapampangan youth was able to inherit.

Such word has strong impact on the socio-cultural beliefs that the language users are portraying. The sense of being superstitious is the one that is being preserved or maintained. This belief according to the elders of the community is also evident in other regions or communities in the Philippines.

Keni/Mekeni

When people call out their group of friends, they use the word “mekeni” to address them. In other setting, words like “keni” , “pards “mekeni” or “dabarkads mekeni” are also being used to mean friends come with me or come with us. The word “mekeni” is often associated to an “individual” or a “group” that is known in Pampanga as bound by friendships and acquaintances.

Diyablus

It refers to a word that is generally understood by the people as a “bad person” or “bitch”. It is said to be adapted from another word “diyablo” which means Satan or demon. In general, this word is used to refer to someone who is not doing good to others. A person who manifests an evil act or a not so favorable attitude.

Salibatbat

This is the Pampango way of penitence (*penitensya*) that is usually being done during Holy week or *Mahal na araw*. Many people express religiousness during this special occasion and some of them join the group of those who will be having *pamagsalibatbat* or penitence. The performers intentionally hurt themselves believing that it will reduce their sins. The devotees have different way of portraying “*Salibatbat*”.

Atin yang ditak

The Filipino translation of this word is “*meron siyang konti*” (he has a little). In Pampango expression, this word is used to refer to someone who is mentally retarded or Psychotic. This expression is used to refer to describe that somebody is suffering from psychological problem or mental illness.

Meanings and Formation Processes of the Pampango Slang Words and Socio-Cultural Expressions

The language Users and their Slang Words and Socio-cultural Expressions.

Austin (1975) pointed out illocutionary acts which are manifested through the use of language. The value of act is always associated with the words that people use. Slang words are parts of the language that people use in conveying intention of speech and utterances of feelings. These words have expressive functions to persuade and convince the listeners.

Table 1 presents the words or expressions which were analyzed based on the categories of speech acts. The types of interlocutors and utterance were also indicated for interpretation. It can also be noted that the researcher was able to show the distinctions of such Pampango terminologies and expressions according to their functions or usages.

Table 1. Based on Searle (1969) five categories of speech act and Halliday's function of language.

Word/ Expression	Category	Interlocutor/s	Utterance	Function
Opu/pu	Declaratives	Young Ones	"Makilabas kami pu" (Can we pass by)	Informing
Meyatu	Declaratives	Elder	"Meyatu ya". (Nabati siya/He was harmed by an unseen being)	Informing
Patawas me	Imperatives	Elder	"Nung masakit ya, patawas me" (Bring him to the faith healer if he is sick)	Advising
Baribari apu	Expressives	Children/Elders	Bari-bari apu, makilabas ke pu (Asking permission. We will just pass by)	Informing
Tawu	Interrogatives	Elder	Nanong tawu yu (What food did you prepare?)	Asking
Taksyapo	Expressives	Elder/ Student	Taksyapo, ot e minta? (Oh my goodness, why he did not come?)	Questioning
Dyandirit	Expressives	Student	Dyandirit e na gawan ita eh! (Oh whatever happens, he will not do that)	Declaring
Misdan a yatut	Informatives	Student	Kamulalan na ne.Misdan a yatut. (He is so naive)	Informing
Pasirkulatok	Imperatives	Elder	Pasirkulatok ye ba yang e sasakit (Please ask to have his name changed so that he will not get sick anymore)	Commanding
Borboolen	Declaratives	Student	A borboolen. E mo baluing gagawan mo. (You're crazy. You don't know what you are doing)	Informing
O-jo	Expressives	Elder	O-jo kaluguran daka (Moh Hon, I love you.)	Declaring
Alang atdo	Informatives	Elder	Ala yang atdong mapait ing anak a ini	Informing

			(This child is not doing good)	
Arya	Informatives	Elder	Karakal da arya. (They have a lot of superstitions)	Declaring
Keni	Commissives	Student	Keni tol, mangan tana (Come on brother, let`s eat).	Convincing
Diyablus	Declaratives	Elder	Ala neng gawang masanting ing diyablus (He did not do anything good.)	Informing
Salibatbat	Declaratives	Elder	Megsalibatbat ya. (He did it as form of penitence)	Informing
Atin yang ditak	Informatives	Elder	Atin yang ditak ing kapatad na. (His brother is psychotic)	Informing

The general functions of language according to Halliday (1975) are the instrumental, regulatory, representational, interactional, personal, heuristic and imaginative functions. The instrumental function of language is the “I want function” which is used for suggesting, demanding, persuading, commanding and directing. Regulatory function is for approving and disapproving, answering phone and addressing an action. The representational is used for informing, explaining and making statements while interactional function is for inviting, accepting and joking. The actions like exclaiming, expressing anger and apologizing are under the personal function of language. When a person argues, defines and concludes, heuristic function is applied. On the other hand, the words expressed in literary works and philosophical systems are all imaginative functions of language.

The table below also showcased the words and expressions identified according to language users. Also, presented are the formation processes of the determined Pampango slang words and socio-cultural expressions. The meanings of the determined socio-cultural expressions were also indicated. Based on the analysis of data, the selected Pampango expressions have relevant meanings in the conversation and the words have different formation processes such as word adaptation, borrowing, language blending, coining, word association and connotation. Other terminologies were given other meanings or interpretations that are quite far from their literal meanings.

Table 2. Pampango Slang Words and Socio-cultural Expressions

Pampango Slang Words and Socio-Cultural Expressions	Meaning of Word for the Language Users	Formation Process
Opu/pu	Yes (in civilized form of address, respectful word)	Adaptation (from the Tagalog word po at opo)
Meyatu	Harmed by an unseen being (nabati in Tagalog)	Definite
Patawas me	Bring to the faith healer/traditional healer	Borrowing from other word /Connotation(word association)
Baribari apu	Tabi tabi po in Tagalog (sorry for the disturbance. We`ll just pass by)	Definite
Tawu	Handa (Food prepared during fiesta)	Definite
Taksyapo/Taklnaydo	What the hell/bitch	Indefinite
Dyandirit	What ever happens	Indefinite
Misdan a yatut	Naïve	Word association/connotation
Pasirkulatok	Change nick name	Definite
Borbolen	Crazy	Indefinite
O jo	Oh my love	Language blending
Alang atdo	Walang apdo (Without bile)	Connotation/putting other meaning to the expressions
Arya	Superstitious belief (Pamahiin)	Definite
Keni	Come with me	Definite
Diyablus	Bad person	Coining
Salibatbat	Penitence	Definite
Atin yang ditak	Psychotic	Word association

It appeared that words “po” at “opo” in Tagalog are also being used in the Kapampangan dialect as a respectful response to the elders in the community. Other words and expressions such as “taksyapo”, “misdan a yatut”, “borbolen”, “alang atdo”, “dyablus” and “atin yang ditak” are negative expressions which could have serious or funny meanings depending on the contexts.

Some terminologies were just coined or adapted to give lights and twists to words like “diyablus” and “o-jo”. There are words which are products of word association, connotation, blending and borrowing like “patawas me”, “misdan a yatut”, “o jo”, “alang atdo” and “atin yang ditak”. Other expressions are said to have indefinite formations such as “taksyapo”, “dyandirit” and “borbolen” while the words “arya”, “keni”, “meyatu”, “baribari apu”, “tawu”, “pasirkulatok” and “salibatbat” are considered to be definite Pampango words.

Conclusions and Recommendations

The selected slang words and socio-cultural expressions of the Pampangos are evident based on the result of the qualitative study. These socio-cultural words are definitely part of the Pampango sociolects that reflect how rich the Kapampangan language is in terms of culture and tradition. In addition, those words and expressions have value and functions in a speech community with a unique tradition and heritage.

Pampango slang words and socio-cultural expressions have varied meanings depending on the contexts in which the words are used. The words which appeared in the study are strong proofs that Kapampangan being one of the languages in Central Luzon is truly a living language that exists.

The different formation processes of the Pampango slang words and socio-cultural expressions would show the dynamicity and inventive minds of the Pampangos. Words are being borrowed, adapted and formed because that is the nature of language. The dynamicity of Pampango dialect can lead to even broader research on Pampango idiolect and sociolect. Consistent study on Pampango terminologies will give language committee a reason to adapt words which have value for formalization and may be added in the lexicon of the Pampango language and this will serve as a guide in crafting a Pampango socio-cultural dictionary.

Extensive research on the origin, adaptation and formation of the Pampango slang words and socio-cultural expressions may give clearer explanations or justifications on their grammatical structures. Moreover, further analysis on the use of slang may lead to the understanding of this linguistic phenomenon with the focus on preserving local culture and values. Having a deep understanding of the sociolect might justify even more the strong influence of changes in the society as contributory factors to language development.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Prior to the gathering of data, the researcher prepared the designed materials. Most importantly, the researcher has prepared for the interview questions which served as the primary tools of the research. There was also an appointment set and he also asked permission from the respondents following an ethical form of address. The researcher considered as well the rules in terms of handling confidential information, proper procedure and documentation.

Moreover, the respondents were also advised or informed regarding the mechanics in answering the research questions. The researcher also made sure that the respondents' answers were used strictly for research purposes and not for personal gains

or interest. It was also rest assured that the sources were properly acknowledged or duly cited.

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